

DEVELOPMENT AND PROSPECTS OF THE HOSPITALITY INDUSTRY IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract. This article examines the tourist market, the capacity of tourist infrastructure, the needs of tourists, the preparation of projects for foreign investments in the production of new tourist services and products, the development of advertising programs for Uzbekistan or its individual regions and their personal image in the world tourism market.

Keywords: Tourism, market, infrastructure, service, program, efficiency, hotel, business.

РАЗВИТИЕ И ПЕРСПЕКТИВЫ ИНДУСТРИИ ГОСТЕПРИИМСТВА В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ

Аннотация. В данной статье рассматривается туристский рынок, возможности туристической инфраструктуры, потребности туристов, подготовка проектов для иностранных инвестиций в производство новых туристических услуг и продуктов, разработка рекламных программ для Узбекистана или отдельных его регионов и их личного имиджа на мировом туристическом рынке.

Ключевые слова: Туризм, рынок, инфраструктура, сервис, программа, эффективность, гостиница, бизнес.

INTRODUCTION

The existence of both the necessity and the opportunities for the tourism and hospitality business, the continuous increase of the requirements for it, imposes the requirements to strengthen the economy and increase the efficiency of the tourist complexes that carry out these types of activities, to organize the management tools that serve this, such as tourism marketing in accordance with today's requirements. This demand, in turn, necessitates deep research of the problems of economic development and efficiency improvement of tourist complexes, as well as theoretical, organizational and methodological issues of marketing in them.

These characteristics of the tourist product have a great influence on the content of tourism marketing. Based on this, tourism marketing is a set of methods and methods of organizing the promotion of tourist services in order to meet the demand for recreation and recreation in the tourist market.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Systematic approach, abstract-logical thinking, grouping, comparison, factor analysis, selective observation methods were used in the research process.

RESULTS

Consists of:

In the tourist market, the needs for recreation and recreation include offering methods and methods of organizing the promotion of tourist services in order to meet the demand for changing the environment.

In order to achieve this goal, the following tasks were defined and performed in the article:

Development and prospects of the hospitality industry in Uzbekistan.

Creating a marketing complex in the hospitality industry.

Expanding the range of hospitality services and development of additional tourist services. Show ways to improve marketing activities in tourist enterprises.

The tourism sector of the Republic of Uzbekistan is an integral part of the world tourism process, and the prediction of BTT experts fully confirms this.

The analyzes show that despite all the political and socio-economic instability in recent years, the country's tourism sector is one of the sectors of the national economy that is increasing the volume of production of products and services without state investments and subsidies. Uzbekistan has all the necessary resources for the development of a modern tourism industry. Our homeland, located on the Great Silk Road, has favorable natural and climatic conditions, a rich historical and cultural heritage, and at the same time a high potential for the development of both domestic and international tourism.

Given the importance given to the above factors, a number of measures are being implemented in the Republic of Uzbekistan to develop the tourism sector. Due to the rapidly changing external and internal environment in the context of the global financial and economic crisis, it is necessary to recognize that there are a number of problems with the development of the tourism market of Uzbekistan. In turn, such a situation leads to a decrease in the amount of foreign currency investments made by our country and foreign investors in the tourism sector. The development of tourism around the world brings great benefits and contributes to the development of the national economy. This, in turn, is important for the economy of Uzbekistan today.

The tourism market needs to be managed on the basis of continuous development and control, in which it is necessary to use the principles of scientific and rational planning. Only then can tourism bring great economic benefits to the state, as well as have a positive impact on the environmental conditions and socio-cultural processes in society. The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Tourism" establishes the state policy in the field of tourism based on the development of national, regional and local programs for the development of tourism, the creation of a regulatory and legal framework for the establishment of this highly profitable economic sector. implies implementation.

In recent years, state structures have been changing dramatically in relation to tourism. They see in tourism the growth of the national economy, the formation of market relations, a practical way to get large amounts of money to the state budget, the rational use of free time, a meaningful way to spend leisure time, and ways to attract the population to the historical and cultural values of the country. . Foreign experts consider the Republic of Uzbekistan to be one of the countries with bright prospects in terms of tourism due to its rare natural resources and historical and cultural heritage.

In the conditions of the national and cultural revival of Uzbekistan, the role of domestic tourism is increasing. That's why the plans of Uzbekistan's tourist companies envisage comprehensive support of its social, economic and cognitive functions, because they are the ones who will suffer the most in the transition of market relations. Nowadays, most people who want to travel do not choose the routes of historical knowledge and healing, health restoration, they prefer to go abroad for more trade and profit.

XX! The main goal of tourist activity in the Republic of Uzbekistan in the 20th century is to create an organizational, legal and economic environment for the further development of the hospitality industry, to form a competitive tourist services market based on the effective use of

the natural, historical and cultural potential of our republic, to promote its socio-economic interests and environmental safety. is to provide. To achieve these goals, it is necessary to solve the following main tasks:

- introduction of effective mechanisms of financial and economic regulation of the tourist industry, identification of sources of financing, creation of the most optimal option of investment policy in this sector:
- improvement of organizational structures of network management:
- ensuring the optimal use of the historical and historical-cultural potential of tourism by dividing the territory of the country into tourism destinations on a scientific basis.

The following are the reasons that hinder the development of tourism in Uzbekistan:

- non-compliance of the level of hotel and transport service, tourist food and recreation system with world standards;
- to increase their price due to the low level of service;
- lack of national marketing information system and various forms of advertising;
- the fact that the qualifications of the employees of many tourism firms do not meet today's requirements and, as a result, these firms mainly target foreign tourism.

In the conditions of the transformation of economic relations, an important factor in increasing the efficiency of management of tourism development is the search for new forms of economic management. In the market of tourist services in our country, mainly traditional forms are currently operating. If the price of passes is constantly increasing, the number of vacationers will also decrease. It follows from the above that one of the most urgent problems in Uzbekistan in the current conditions is to reorganize the tourism industry and increase its profitability, primarily through the creation of high-tech complexes and tourist centers with appropriate infrastructure.

Another unique feature of Uzbekistan's tourist potential is that the country has all forms of relief in nature (mountains, plains, deserts, hills, steppes). Fergana Valley, Bostanliq, Zomin, Urgut, Kitab, Boysun regions have sufficient conditions for the development of mountain, sports, ecotourism and recreation. 121 of the more than 300 healing mineral groundwaters in our republic are used to restore public health.

Taking into account the above opportunities, more than 40 percent of the incoming tourists will visit Samarkand, Bukhara and Khorezm, 17 percent will go to the Fergana Valley, and the rest will go to other regions. Samarkand and Bukhara regions lead the way in terms of receiving tourists, the volume of services provided to them, and profit, while the lowest indicators are observed in Andijan, Jizzah and Tashkent regions.

Most of the international tourists visit the city of Tashkent. The reason is that the capital and Tashkent region account for 36% of the total tourist infrastructure and sufficient conditions have been created. Fergana Valley has 19 percent of the republic's tourist infrastructure. However, the capacity and level of the existing tourist infrastructure cannot fully satisfy the needs of foreign tourists.

In order to eliminate the problems that have arisen, it is necessary to create a system of providing additional services at the level of interests and demands of international tourists. It is also important to prepare projects for foreign investments in the production of new tourist services and products, to develop advertising programs for Uzbekistan or its individual regions and their personal image in the world tourism market.

Today, 200 of the tourist facilities in our country are being restored, and 500 are in need of repair and restoration. Billions of funds are allocated from the state budget for these works. But this area cannot be limited to the budget. It should be self-sustaining as well as hard currency and cash generating industry.

It should be noted separately that in many countries the restoration process is also used as a tourist attraction. It shows the original design of this object, its current condition, the restoration process and how it should be. Of course, these conditions are important for historical objects. This naturally attracts tourists.

Along with the great tourism potential of Uzbekistan, some of its cities are very interesting. For example, the city of Khiva ranks first in terms of the number of objects that tourists can see. It has 310 objects, Bukhara city is in second place with 221 objects, Tashkent city has 144 objects and Samarkand has 118 objects.

Apart from these existing tourist facilities, several more facilities can be established. If we consider Samarkand province alone, it has scenic mountain passes such as Urgut, Oman-qO'ton, Okhalik, Mironkul, to which it is possible to organize walking routes. But such authority was not taken.

Of course, in the summer season, these gorges are very crowded. But these are voluntary vacationers. It is still not possible to organize trips to these mountain landscapes in an organized way. Such objects are also available in Bakhmal, Zomin, Forish districts of Jizzakh region, valley regions, many scenic districts of Tashkent region. It's about putting them to work and using them for the population and the economy of our country.

Table 1

By travel agencies and hotels in Samarkand region About services provided in the field of tourism in 2017-2021

INFORMATION

No	Indicators	Measurement unit.	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
1.	Volume of services provided in general	million soum	6920.8	11047.8	14614.3	13348.5	17826.3
2.	Earned income	million soum	1038.8	1162.6	1039.1	1007.3	1465.8
3.	Export of services	US dollars	5028000	4726580	7984252	4704219	6436083
4.	Number of tourists	person	68725	95314	101732	95072	117191
5.	Foreign tourists	person	42937	66191	68711	58849	67368
6.	Tourists from MDX	person	2753	4582	5956	6117	8244
7.	Uzbeks	person	23035	24541	27065	30106	41579

One of the unique features of our country is the development of the oriental market. These objects are unique to us in many respects and naturally interest tourists from other regions. These places are ready for tourist viewing. The inclusion of markets in tourist facilities has two benefits. Firstly, if there is an opportunity to show our rich gifts to tourists, secondly, there will be an opportunity to sell oriental sweets and provide foreign currency income. For this purpose, it is advisable to organize money exchange offices in the appropriate place of the market, which is included in each tourist object.

There are more than 300 spas, more than 40 sanatoriums, hundreds of holiday homes in our country. But most of these objects are not involved in tourism. However, many of our spas are located in amazingly beautiful places and also cure many diseases. However, as it was noted, due to the fact that the advertisement was not properly implemented, tourists were not attracted to these places at all, we were not able to turn any resort facilities into an international arena, a recreation zone. This is a sign that a lot of work needs to be done. The tourism potential of our country is so high and diverse that it should be used wisely only for this purpose. The main ones are shown in this drawing

Figure 1.

As can be seen in this drawing, the directions for the development of tourism in our country are very wide. It covers everything from tourist vacation to hiking, from simple observation to scientific expedition. This figure is only 2.0 percent. There is not enough advertising and accurate information about the remaining tourist objects and valuable monuments. So, it seems that there is still a lot of work to be done in this regard. The services of scientists such as historians, archaeologists, and antiquarians should be sufficient for this.

The number of foreigners who expressed their desire to come to our country on a tourist route is 10.0 million. constitutes a person. This is a huge opportunity, now the task is to use this opportunity wisely.

Today, more than 710 tourist organizations operate in the country, of which 261 have a license to provide hotel services. In recent years, the tourism industry of Uzbekistan has been growing steadily.

Another important feature of Uzbekistan is that the "Great Silk Road" passes through it, and its center is also considered to be in this region. If this is restored and a single route called "Along the Great Silk Road" is established, this will be a great opportunity to attract tourists. The potential of ecotourism in Uzbekistan. In our country, there are not only world-famous ancient cities such as Samarkand, Bukhara, Khiva, Termiz, which attract foreign tourists, historical monuments, but at the same time, unique beautiful nature, landscapes (desert, desert - hills, mountains, low plains), a variety of unique flora and fauna, rare, world-important archaeological finds, paleontological remains, rare geological sections in the world, more than 800 natural monuments.

In addition, Uzbekistan is located in the middle of Central Asia in a convenient transport-geographical area for the development of ecotourism, it is connected by various developed transport and transport communication routes, and it is a world leader in terms of its international tourism potential. takes place.

Although the above-mentioned tourist indicators have great potential for ecotourism in our country and occupy a high place in the global ecotourism industry in terms of its potential, in practice, measures and activities for the full use of these potentials and opportunities have not been implemented in Uzbekistan.

Table 2
List of protected natural areas of the Republic of Uzbekistan

No	Name	Place of protection	Field, ga	Year of establishment
State reserves 175536				
1	Baday - a forest	Forest ecosystems of the Amudarya lowlands	6462	1971
2	Hisar	Mountain ecosystems of the Hisar range	80986	1983
3	Zomin	Mountain ecosystems of the Turkestan Range	21735	1959
4	Zarafshon	The middle course of the Zarafshan River forest ecosystems	2352	1875
5	Kyzylkum	Forest ecosystems of the Amudarya middle course and neighboring deserts	10311	1971
6	Light	Nurota mountain ecosystems	21137	1975
7	Surkhan	Mountain ecosystems of the Kohitong range and forest ecosystems of the Amudarya middle stream	26895	1987
8	Book	A unique geological deposit	3938	1979
9	Ugom-Chotkal State Nature Park	Western Tianshan Ecosystem	574590	1990
10	People's Park	Ecosystem of the Turkestan Ridge	24110	1977

	(Zomin)			
State nature monuments			3058	
11	The desert of Yozhyovon	A unique natural sand massif	1962	1994
12	Mingbulok district natural monument	Flora and fauna	1000	1991
13	Chust district natural monument	Flora and fauna	96	1990
Order offices			1503206	
14	oktog'	Animal and plant world	15400	1997
15	Dengizkol	Animal and plant world	50000	1990
16	Cauliflower	Animal and plant world	40000	1992
17	Karakir	Animal and plant world	30000	1992
18	Help	Animal and plant world	16300	1997
19	Blessed	Rare and endangered mammals	264469	1997
20	Garlic	Animal and plant world	5000	1997
21	Saigachi	Wild animals	1000000	1997
22	Sechankol	Fish	7037	1998
23	Sudochbe	Wild animals	50000	1991
24	Hubara	Tuvalok and its habitats	25000	1998
Natural nurseries			7122	
25	"Jayron" eco-center	Horses of gazelle, bulak, prezhevalsk	7122	1976
26	Fishing areas			
27	Protected landscapes		1004005	
28	Resort nature areas		338	
29	Recreation areas		70	
30	State biosphere reserves		35724	
31	Chotkal State Biosphere Reserve	Chotkal system ecosystems	35724	1947

DISCUSSION

One of the main factors hindering the development of ecological tourism in Uzbekistan is the lack of free living of rare animals in Central Asia, which are the most important for ecotourists in our national natural parks and protected natural areas. It is due to lack of infrastructure, conditions, and material and technical base. Therefore, starting from 2016, initial steps were taken to develop this sector, and the trends of gradual development of ecotourism in Uzbekistan are being observed.

Table 3

Key indicators of the tourism development program of the international organization "Ekosan" for 2017-2021.

	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021.	2017-2021 years.
Number of tourists	200	300	550	1100	2850	5000

Increase in the flow of tourists (in % compared to the previous year)	106	150.0	183.3	200.0	259.1	1425
Volume of tourist services (million sums)	2.1	3.1	6.2	12.5	25.5	48.9
% compared to previous year		150.0	200.0	200.0	200.0	1200.0
Also, the volume of transport services (million sums)	1.5	2.4	4.8	7.2	9.6	25.5
% compared to previous year		164.8	200.0	150.0	133.3	659.3
Purchase of vehicles (unit)		1	2	3	2	8

As can be seen from the table, in the period of 2017-2021, the attraction of tourists to ecological tourism is increasing year by year, naturally, the volume of services is also increasing, and the profit received has also increased. This result is achieved by improving the quality of service and using marketing activities. This shows that ecotourism is one of the promising sectors in Uzbekistan.

CONCLUSION

So, our country's ability to develop tourism is incomparable. It is natural that the effective use of it, the establishment of the tourism industry will become one of the main areas that will ensure the economic growth of our country.

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